

DIPLOMATIC AND POLITICAL RELATIONS OF UZBEKISTAN WITH WESTERN COUNTRIES.

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Abstract: In globalization period interrelationship among countries are important. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between Uzbekistan and Western countries in different administrations

Key words: the European Union, relationship, New Uzbekistan, administrations.

Introduction: Relations between the European Union and the Republic of Uzbekistan have been developing steadily since its independence in 1991. The EU has accepted Uzbekistan as the 9th beneficiary country of the special incentive arrangement for sustainable development and good governance.

Under the former administration, Uzbekistan became an economically and politically isolated country with a minimal volume of foreign trade and low foreign direct investments. Therefore, Uzbekistan's relationship with the EU and other western country is inferior.

Uzbekistan's political and economic opening under the new leadership President Shavkat Mirziyoyev came as a surprise. Since he has taken office in 2016, Uzbekistan has undoubtedly been in a phase of profound change. Furthermore, Uzbekistan has improved and intensified its external relations in all directions, including the EU.

The former administration

During the Karimov's long rule, Uzbekistan's foreign policy was based on strengthening its national independence and sovereignty, maximizing its national security and preventing external actors from having interference in internal affairs. To strengthen his country's national independence and sovereignty, Karimov had been determined to pursue some form of self-reliance policy since the early years of the independence. In early year of Karimov's era Uzbekistan tried to stay away from Russia because the rationale behind his self-reliance policy had been to break away from the 'imperial' Soviet center, relinquish dependency and promote its own model of development. This is evident in Former British Ambassador to Uzbekistan Paul Bergen's memoirs in which he described Tashkent's stance right after the independence: "President Karimov's first priority was firmly to establish Uzbek independence. And clearly the first step in doing that was to create a distance between him and Moscow as the colonial power" (Pannier,2000) Because of this Karimov tried to collaborate with European Union and Western countries in his early years.

Negotiation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and Government of the European Union was signed on June 21, 1996 in Florence. The deepening and development of Uzbekistan's relations with Western European countries contributed to the activation of trade. For example, in 1998. Uzbekistan exported goods worth \$ 537.4 million to European countries, while the share of imports in the same period was \$ 335.0 million.

The establishment and development of relations with the European Union contributed to the growth of Uzbekistan's authority on a global scale. The signing of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between Uzbekistan and the European Union at such a high-level forum is certainly an important event that marks a new, repeated stage of our relations. Moreover, Uzbekistan entered into cooperation with 15 European states on a formal legal basis. The agreement provides for cooperation in political, legal, economic, financial and technical and many other areas. The parties agreed to create favorable conditions for mutual trade and free transit of goods on the territory of their countries. In general, Uzbekistan, thanks to rapprochement with the European Union, has gained access to advanced European experience and modern technologies.

Over the year of independence, Uzbekistan and the United States have developed ties in the political, economic and military fields. In 1992, ambassadors of the two countries were accredited in Tashkent and Washington, in April 1995, US Secretary of Defense William Perry visited Uzbekistan, after which the United States was visited by the Minister of Defense of our county. An important event was the meeting of the President of Uzbekistan with US vice President Albert Gore, which was held at the White house in October 1995.

In June 1996, Karimov paid an official visit to the United States of America, where he met with Bill Clinton. The meeting was more important for the development of bilateral relations between the two countries and for the integration of the young independent state into the world community. Despite the good relations between the United States and Uzbekistan in the 1990s, relations have been deteriorating year by year. There were several reasons for this.

From the end of the 1990s until the Andijan event in mid-2005, Uzbekistan under Karimov had sought closer ties with the West, particularly the US and NATO. Before September 11, the country collaborated with the US in regional anti-terrorism efforts in order to alleviate its concerns about the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU), which had relations with the Taliban then. In

the aftermath of September 11, Tashkent had sought to secure closer cooperation with the West to address common threats and concerns and to maximize its national security accordingly. Uzbekistan granted its territory and airspace to the US forces in the fight against terrorism, and in 2002, two countries signed a Declaration on Strategic Partnership and Cooperation Framework which came about in the context of September 11 and the launch of Operation Enduring Freedom(OEF).

Unfortunately, the West's attitude towards the Uzbek government's response to the events in Andijan in May 2005 had led not only to the deterioration of the US-Uzbek relations, but also Uzbekistan's relations with the West as a whole. The divergence between Uzbekistan and the West surfaced after the Uzbek government declared that the armed uprising in Andijan was a terrorist outbreak

responded with force (Gleason, 2006). The US's call on the Uzbek government to allow an international investigation of events in Andijan was openly assessed by Karimov as foreign interference in Uzbekistan's internal affairs.

After these events Karimov's administration had changed their way, from 2005 to at the end of Karimov's era they tried to collaborate with Russia and other Eastern countries.

Remarkable diplomatic changes in new Uzbekistan

After sudden death of former President Islam Karimov, in December 2016, Prime Minister Shavkat Mirziyoyev became the new President of Uzbekistan. After he was elected as the new president of Uzbekistan in December, some argued that Uzbekistan would establish good relationship with Russia because of personal friendship between him and Russian elites appeared. Meanwhile, others suggested that the country would follow Karimov's path like Turkmenistan. However, both options were wrong and Mirziyoyev have announced dramatic changes. Under Mirziyoyev Uzbekistan is trying to be open and democratic country in order to do this Uzbekistan has started close and wide collaboration with Western counties. Yet, European union and Western countries have geopolitical and economic benefits here in Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan has been through significant policy changes over the past five years. Under the leadership of Shavkat Mirziyayev, the country has moved from

an isolated dictatorship into young democracy, from a shadow economy into a liberalized market. Sh.Mirziyoyev presented key points of his program “Strategy of New Uzbekistan”. The main message in his speech was that nowadays the democratic reforms in the country have acquired an irreversible, stable character and the state intends to steadily continue their implementation. Indeed, over the past five years, under the leadership of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the living conditions of the Uzbek people have improved, their worldwide has widened, the atmosphere of openness has become an integral part of life of society.

If we look at the economic and political collaboration between the EU and Uzbekistan, relationship is developing very sharply. Uzbekistan is a perfect place for European businesses. The country has created one of the most favorable business environments in the region. It attracts foreign investors and companies that strive for more ambitious regional targets. An important stage in economic cooperation between the parties was the granting for Uzbekistan the status of a beneficiary country of the General System of Preferences “GSP+” on April, 2021. This contributed to a noticeable increase in the volume of Uzbek exports to the EU. The number of commodity items that can be duty-free exported to the EU countries increase to 6200 items. The EU monitoring mission on “GSP+” visited Uzbekistan and prepared positive assessments on Uzbekistan in March 2022. As a result, in the first six months of this year trade turnover between Uzbekistan and EU countries increased by 22%, while exports from Uzbekistan grew by 86%.

Meanwhile, Uzbekistan attempts to join World Trade Organization for a long time. The WTO has many economic benefits for Uzbekistan, first of all, it helps to gradually eliminate monopolies in Uzbekistan and to regulate the huge import duties, as well as to liberalize internal and external trade. As for the second side of the argument, that is, the political side. Due to the protectionist policy of the first administration, there were suggestions to join this organization, but no practical works were done. The main reasons for this is the country’s management system, because Uzbekistan has not yet accepted as a member despite the fact that it applied for the WTO membership in 1995 (since 27), while Kyrgyzstan was accepted to the WTO within 2 years. However, during the current administration, both practical and theoretical work is being done to join this organization.

In terms of values, since 2016, Mirziyoyev followed an innovative policy to transform Uzbekistan’s decision-making processes and the rule of law issues.

In doing so, he has already reshaped the domestic political landscape, changed the fundamental relationship between the citizen and state. Uzbekistan is indeed confidentially and surely moving towards democracy. Furthermore, the country has proved many times that when it comes to climate, business, education it clearly prefers to cooperate with the EU. Meanwhile EU benefit here for in order to tackle energetic dependency Russian EU prefer to collaborate with Uzbekistan.

To conclude, relations between Uzbekistan and Western countries is developing year by year in every field. Both sides benefit from this cooperation.

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